

New European Bauhaus Call for proposals for Citizen Engagement Activities

Project Acronym: SOCIAL4FOOD

**Project title: SOCIAL farming FOR stimulating transgenerational knowledge
transfer and production of typical local FOOD**

Deliverable 1.1: DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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1. Executive summary

The SOCIAL4FOOD project aims at applying the principles of New European Bauhaus to improve the contact between young generations and green public spaces, guided by the wisdom of the elders. Through a series of social farming activities, the project aims to stimulate the involvement of teenagers from the Town of Arsoli (including also young immigrants) in collaboratively farming and cooking a very ancient and high-quality bean typical of this town, named “fagiolina arsolana”. The data generated and collected during the project will be used for research purposes and dissemination of results.

This document is the SOCIAL4FOOD data management plan (DMP). The DMP describes the data management life cycle for all datasets to be collected, processed and/or generated by the research project.

Specifically, it describes, among others:

- *the handling of research data during and after the project;*
- *the type of data that will be collected, processed, or gathered;*
- *what methodology and standards will be applied;*
- *whether and how the data will be made (openly) accessible;*
- *how data is stored.*

2. Data Summary

The project will collect and generate data that are specified in the following table, along with the general specifications and structures of the metadata that will be generated.

<p>What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?</p>	<p>The SOCIAL4FOOD project will generate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data D1 from the identification of target groups for the specific objective SO1 (Engagement of citizens and key stakeholders in SOCIAL4FOOD training activities); - Data D2 from ideas elicitation and need analysis for the specific objective SO1 (Engagement of citizens and key stakeholders in SOCIAL4FOOD training activities); - Data D3 from social green laboratories and SOCIAL4FOOD competition for the specific objectives SO1 (Engagement of citizens and key stakeholders in SOCIAL4FOOD training activities) and SO3 (Experimenting with a citizen engagement strategy to promote the culture and knowledge of typical local foods and traditional agricultural knowledge for replicating it in other similar contexts); - Data D4 from the co-creation of the social farm for the specific objective SO2 (Re-purposing of abandoned green spaces); - Data D5 from the qualitative survey for feedback and possible refinements for the specific objective SO3 (Experimenting with a citizen engagement strategy to promote the culture and knowledge of typical local foods and traditional agricultural knowledge for replicating it in other similar contexts); - Data D6 from the final outreach event for the general public for the specific objective SO3 (Experimenting with a citizen engagement strategy to promote the culture and knowledge of typical local foods and traditional agricultural knowledge for replicating it in other similar contexts).
<p>What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?</p>	<p>The project will generate the following types of data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data D1: name, surname and email (personal data); - Data D2: photos, images, videos, drawings,

	<p>written documents;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data D3, D4 and D6: photos, images, videos; - Data D5: questionnaires, and interviews. <p>Data D1 and metadata will be requested, stored and transferred in comma-separated values CSV format;</p> <p>Data D2 will be stored and transferred in jpeg and mp4 and pdf format;</p> <p>Data D3, D4 and D6 will be stored and transferred in jpeg and mp4 format;</p> <p>Data D5 will be stored and transferred in pdf format.</p>
Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<p>Collected data D2, D3, D4 and D5 will be analysed and re-used for an open access publication.</p> <p>Collected data D2, D3, D4 and D6 will be re-used for the dissemination of the project activities and results on the project website, social media accounts, brochures, and local press.</p>
What is the origin of the data?	<p>Data will be collected from the Open Day event, the social green laboratories, the SOCIAL4FOOD competition, the co-creation of the social farm, the qualitative survey, and the final outreach event.</p>
What is the expected size of the data?	<p>The expected size of data is approximately twenty gigabytes (due to the large videos of the events, images, and photos).</p>
To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?	<p>The collected data might be useful for:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) the scientific sector as a reference for good practices and lessons learnt in citizen engagement processes; 2) local administrators and policymakers for transferring the participatory methodology to their local contexts.

3. FAIR data

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

<p>Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and</p>	<p>Participants to the SOCIAL4FOOD project will be informed about the activities in which they participate, raising ethical concerns regarding informed consent.</p>
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<p>unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?</p>	<p>The data with the consent of the person concerned will be collected into several datasets according to the type of data and will be made discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable -using a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). In particular, the metadata and datasets will be uploaded to the ZENODO (https://zenodo.org/) platform.</p> <p>The data without the consent of the person concerned will be collected in a private and secure dataset on an offline pc in a locked room of the IRPPS.</p>
<p>What naming conventions do you follow?</p>	<p>To make it easy to identify the file(s), the following file naming convention will be used that contains the information about the project, the type of activity/event, and the type of data title, as follows:</p> <p>Project_TypeOfEvent_TypeOfData</p> <p>For instance, we will use:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SOCIAL4FOOD_OpenDayEvent_photos • SOCIAL4FOOD_OpenDayEvent_images • SOCIAL4FOOD_OpenDayEvent_videos <p>for the datasets containing the photos, images or videos related to the Open Day event of the SOCIAL4FOOD project.</p>
<p>Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?</p>	<p>Several search keywords will be provided when uploading the datasets into the ZENODO platform.</p>
<p>Do you provide clear version numbers?</p>	<p>Only the final version of the datasets will be made available -on the ZENODO platform.</p>
<p>What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</p>	<p>The metadata for the datasets will be created using the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) (https://ddialliance.org/), which is an international standard for describing the data produced by surveys and other observational methods in the social, behavioural, economic, and health sciences.</p>

3.2. Making data openly accessible

<p>Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be</p>	<p>By default, data related to the scientific publication will be made openly available.</p>
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<p>shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if relevant provisions are made in the consortium agreement and are in line with the reasons for opting out.</p>	<p>Moreover, participants in the SOCIAL4FOOD project will be asked for their consent to share the collected data (photos, videos, images, etc.).</p> <p>All data for which we will receive the consent to share it from the participants will be made openly accessible.</p> <p>The personal data processed in the project are not made publicly accessible but kept closed and inaccessible to third parties. Moreover, data without the consent of the person concerned cannot be shared and will be maintained in a private and secure dataset on an offline pc in a locked room of the IRPPS.</p>
<p>How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?</p>	<p>All data for which we will receive the consent to share it from the participants will be made openly accessible through the ZENODO platform (https://zenodo.org/).</p>
<p>What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?</p>	<p>Data will be published using standard file formats (csv, pdf, jpeg, mp4, etc.). All data will be accessed using standard tools.</p>
<p>Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?</p>	<p>If a software tool should be needed to access the data, we will provide the required documentation together with the datasets.</p>
<p>Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?</p>	<p>Not relevant for the project.</p>
<p>Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.</p>	<p>Personal data and data without the consent of the person concerned to share it will be stored on a private and secure dataset on an offline pc in a locked room of the IRPPS. Data to be public will be stored on Zenodo.</p>
<p>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?</p>	<p>Zenodo provides the following arrangements to make data openly accessible:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol (OAI-PMH and REST) that is open, free, and universally implementable and allows for an authentication and authorization procedure (if necessary); - metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available, for a lifetime of 20 years at least.
<p>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?</p>	<p>There are no restrictions on the use of the published data.</p>

Is there a need for a data access committee?	A data access committee is not needed because all the information and conditions to access data are provided in this document.
Are there well described conditions for access (i.e. a machine readable license)?	Zenodo provides well-described conditions to access (see http://about.zenodo.org/policies/)
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	To ascertain the identity of the person/machine accessing the data, username and password for persons or authentication keys for machines are used.

3.3. Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?	Data will be collected and shared in a standardised way using standard formats for the different data types (e.g., csv, jpeg, mp4, pdf). As required, reference will be made to any software required to run it. Openly available software will be used to store, access, and run data.
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	Standard vocabularies for data and metadata description will be used following the international standard provided by the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) (https://ddialliance.org/).
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?	To allow inter-disciplinary interoperability, standard vocabularies will be used for all data produced by surveys and other observational methods.
In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?	If standard vocabularies cannot be used to describe some data types, a mapping with more common ontologies will be provided.

3.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	The data will be made available according to Open Licenses such as Creative Commons. Once the data are made openly available, they will remain open.
When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that	The data used in the scientific publication will be made available immediately after the publication in compliance with the specific rules of the international journal that will be chosen

research data should be made available as soon as possible.	for publication. The data used in the website, brochures, and social media will be made available for re-use immediately.
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.	Data published in open-access journals will be usable by third parties according to the chosen open license. The re-use of data produced and/or used in the project (that does not relate to peer-reviewed publications) will be made available on a case-by-case basis.
How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	The project data (e.g. videos and photos of training activities, surveys and participants' interviews) will remain reusable for the lifetime of the repository, which is expected to be a minimum of 20 years. There is no embargo foreseen.
Are data quality assurance processes described?	Data quality will be assured through adherence to standards for data recording, the use of controlled vocabulary and standard terminology. Another quality assurance process will include the peer-review of the scientific publication based on the collected data.
Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address:	None

4. Allocation of resources

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?	The cost for making data FAIR is estimated to be around 2000 Euros for the open access publication fee to be paid to the scientific international journal. The other costs for archiving data in the open access repository (e.g., ZENODO) will be free of charge.
How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).	The costs for making the data FAIR will be covered by the project (we planned 2000 Euros for the publication fee in the budget allocation).
Who will be responsible for data management in your project?	The IRPPS will have the overall responsibility for data management. It will be responsible for (i) updating the data management plan; (ii) organising data backup, storage, and archiving; (iii) depositing the data within the repositories (Zenodo and the IRPPS private archive).

<p>Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?</p>	<p>There are no costs associated with the long-term preservation of the data. The IRPPS will decide on what data will be kept and for how long.</p>
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5. Data security

<p>What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>	<p>The Zenodo repository will provide the following measures for data security:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - all files uploaded to Zenodo are stored in a CERN server that is managed according to the CERN Security Baseline for Servers; - each file copy has two replicas located on different disk servers which are backed up on a nightly basis. <p>The sensitive data will be not made publicly accessible but stored in the IRPPS repository that provides the following measures for data security:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data is protected against unauthorised access using standard login; - Data will be pseudonymised or completely anonymized so as to not interfere with the quality of the research;
<p>Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?</p>	<p>Public data will be safely stored in the Zenodo open access repository for long-term preservation and curation.</p> <p>Private and sensitive data will be safely stored in the IRPPS repository and kept closed and inaccessible to third parties.</p>

6. Ethical aspects

<p>Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).</p>	<p>Some ethical or legal issues could impact the data sharing. Specifically, the transfer of data on human subjects to the IRPPS repository is only considered when informed consent, ethics approval and approval by local data protection authorities (when applicable) are acquired and allow the transfer of individual or aggregated data to the IRPPS repository. All data that are transferred to the IRPPS repository will be either pseudonymised or completely anonymized to comply with the General Data</p>
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	Protection Regulation (GDPR).
Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	Informed consent (both for adults and minors) for data sharing and long-term preservation will be included in the qualitative survey. If any sensitive data is collected it will be separated and kept secure. Moreover, the results of the qualitative survey will be anonymized.

7. Other issues

Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	Data management will be compliant with the European laws regarding data security and the protection of privacy (e.g., GDPR).
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